

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

GEOSPACE RESEARCH: CURRENT STATE AND PROPOSALS TO THE UKRAINIAN ANTARCTIC SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

A. Zalizovski^{1,2,3}, **Y. Yampolski**¹, **O. Koloskov**^{1,2,4}

¹ *Institute of Radio Astronomy of NAS of Ukraine, Kharkiv, Ukraine; zaliz@rian.kharkov.ua;*

² *State Institution National Antarctic Scientific Center, Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine; zalizovski@gmail.com;*

³ *Space Research Centre of Polish Academy of Sciences, Warsaw, Poland; azalizovski@cbk.waw.pl;*

⁴ *University of New Brunswick, NB, Fredericton, Canada; alex.koloskov@unb.ca*

Geospace research has been one of the primary scientific directions at the Faraday-Akademik Vernadsky station (UAS) since the 1950s. During the station handover to Ukraine, the Memorandum on the Transfer identified key areas of research where long-term observations must be continued. Three of them, such as measurements of the total ozone content, vertical sounding of the ionosphere, and geomagnetic observations, are related to geospace research. After the transfer, remote sensing equipment for upper atmosphere study at the UAS was significantly expanded. Since 2001, continuous monitoring of global thunderstorm activity and characteristics of the lower ionosphere in the ELF frequency range has been conducted, later extended to the Arctic region. Today, similar facilities in both hemispheres form a unified global system for diagnosing powerful lightning discharges and monitoring global thunderstorm activity. During the seasonal expedition of 2001–2002, the first test experiments of coherent HF ionospheric sounding were carried out at the UAS and on board the research vessel (RV). At the same time, the original facility for bistatic frequency and angular ionospheric diagnostics was installed at the station. Since 2010, continuous HF Doppler sounding of the ionosphere has become systematic and is continuously performed at UAS using the signals from time service transmitters located in the Northern Hemisphere. VLF measurements at the UAS, which provide valuable information on the ionosphere's D-region, were resumed several years ago. Since 2017, ionospheric vertical sounding facilities at the station have been significantly upgraded. The station is also equipped with GNSS signal receivers, which allow for restoring the total electron content and ionospheric scintillations. In 2022, receiving and measuring equipment was installed on board the RV Noosfera. These efforts significantly expanded the capabilities for local and global monitoring of space weather (SWx) from Antarctica.

Thanks to the recent implementation of reliable high-speed Internet at the UAS, real-time ionospheric data from the station have been incorporated into SWx international services since 2024. As a result, the UAS now functions as a modern, integrated geospace observatory. It is essential to maintain and further develop its capabilities. This report presents our proposals for the new State Program of Ukrainian Antarctic Research. In the coming years, we plan to extend our research to include long-term trends and periodicities in space weather on climate timescales of 30 years and more.

Along with climate changes in the surface part of the atmosphere, it is important to understand space climate trends and anthropogenic activity's impact on it. We intend to continue geospace research in both the Arctic and Antarctic in the framework of international cooperation, aligned with the goals

of the new SCAR Programme Planning Group on Antarctic Geospace and ATmosphere reseArch (AGATA; <https://scar.org/science/research-programmes/agata>). The AGATA program aims to advance the current knowledge of the Antarctic atmosphere and geospace, also in the bi-polar, interhemispheric context.